

eu-citizen.science

The Platform for Sharing, Initiating and Learning Citizen Science in Europe

Deliverable 5.2: Design of training activities and materials

Authors: Nadia Dewhurst-Richman (UCL), Margaret Gold (ECSA), Muki Haklay (UCL), Alice Sheppard (UCL)

Contributors: Dilek Fraisl & Gerid Hager (IIASA), Christian Nold (UCL), Francisco Sanz García (ibercivis).

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Contributors	IIASA, UCL, ibercivis
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Abstract	This deliverable is based on Task 5.2, and includes a detailed typology of training material that is available to different stakeholders and user groups in the field of citizen science, identifying needs, priorities, and gaps. It will also catalogue the existing material that is currently available in different areas of citizen science, and the main thematic organisation that will be used in the platform. It will provide instructions and protocols for building new training modules to be integrated into the platform for external stakeholders.
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Definitions and Acronyms

CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Creative Commons

CSA	Coordination and Support Action
Data	Information, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images. The focus is on research data that is available in digital form. (European Commission, 2016)
Dataset	A grouping of data
Digital Curation	Selection, preservation, maintenance and archiving of electronically stored data
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DS	Data Set
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GD	Google Drive
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPF	Grant Preparation Forms
H2020	Horizon 2020
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
Metadata	A description of data
MoRRI	Monitoring the evolution and benefits of responsible research and innovation
Open Access	Access that is free to all and free of any restrictions
Open Data	Data that can be freely used, shared and built on by anyone for any purpose

OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
PPSR	Public Participation in Scientific Research
Repository	A location in which data is stored or managed
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Table of Contents

Document Identification Sheet	3
Version Log	4
Definitions and Acronyms	4
Executive Summary	10
1. Introduction	10
1.1. The EU-Citizen.Science Project	10
1.2. Purpose of this deliverable	11
2. Training & Educational Material needs	12
2.1. Introduction	12
2.1.1. Training & Educational Material - a definition	12
2.1.2. An update on Training & Educational Material needs since D5.1	13
2.2. Methodology	13
2.2.1. Survey of Training & Educational Material needs	13
2.2.2. Workshop with the EU-Citizen.Science project partners	13
2.2.3. Training & Educational Material needs analysis	14
2.3. Overview of the training material currently available on the EU-Citizen.Science platform	15
2.4. Training & Educational Material needs results	15
2.4.1. Training & Educational Material needs - themes	16
2.4.2. Training & Educational Material needs - audience	19
2.4.3. Training & Educational Material needs - format and type	21
2.4.4. Training & Education Material needs - domain of scientific activity	22
3. Training & Educational Material - metadata requirements	23
3.1. Introduction	23
3.1.1. Best practice in metadata and ontologies	23
3.1.2. Metadata for describing Citizen Science Resources in general	24
3.1.3. Resource Type Categories used in the First Release	26
3.1.4. New Resource Type Categories	27
3.1.5. Metadata for describing Training Materials	28
4. Guidelines for creating a training and educational module for the EU-Citizen.Science platform	36

4.1.	Technical - how to set up a course on Moodle	36
4.1.1.	General	36
4.1.2.	Description	37
4.1.3.	Course format	37
4.1.4.	Appearance	37
4.1.5.	Files and Uploads	37
4.1.6.	Completion tracking	37
4.1.7.	Groups	37
4.1.8.	Role renaming	37
4.1.9.	Tags	38
4.1.10.	Participants	38
4.1.11.	Course badges	38
4.2.	Content design - how to design an online course for Moodle	38
4.2.1.	Content - uploading material to moodle	45
4.3.	Best practice for creating online learning content: feedback from the Consortium	49
5.	Summary and next steps	52
5.1.	Training & Educational Material Needs	52
5.2.	Metadata	54
5.3.	Module content and technical design	55
6.	Appendices	56
6.1.	Appendix 1 - Glossary of themes that describe training materials (taken from Table 4 in D3.2).	56
6.2.	Appendix 2: Example design template: introduction to citizen science for journalists	58
6.2.1.	Core information	58
6.2.2.	Main division - topics	60
6.2.3.	Detailed course plan	61
6.2.4.	Equality Impact Assessment	65
6.2.5.	Digital Assets Register	65
6.2.6.	Detail course content	67
6.3.	Course design checklist (based on UCL's Connected Learning Baseline document)	67

6.3.1.	Navigation	67
6.3.2.	Introduction	69
6.3.3.	Communication	69
6.3.4.	Accessibility	70
6.3.5.	Legal issues	71

Executive Summary

The vision for the EU-Citizen.Science platform is to aid in the mainstreaming of citizen science, and build on the growing impact of citizens participating in research across the full range of scientific enquiry, by supporting the sharing of knowledge, know-how, and experience between anyone doing or wanting to do citizen science. This deliverable is based on Task 5.2, and presents a typology of training and educational material based on a thematic analysis of 1) the material that is already available to the citizen science community, and 2) descriptions of the material needs collected via a questionnaire survey (October 2019) and workshop (June 2020). The questionnaire survey and workshop were also used to identify training and educational material needs and priorities, these are subsequently used to inform the theme and audience of the 20 training modules that will be delivered through the course of the project. This deliverable concludes with a presentation of the metadata requirements for the organisation of training and educational material, balanced on search usability and application of metadata standards that will allow for interoperability. The final section of the deliverable provides instructions and protocols for building new training modules to be integrated into the platform for external stakeholders.

1. Introduction

1.1. The EU-Citizen.Science Project

Citizen science (CS) actively involves the public in scientific research that generates new knowledge or understanding, and thus has the potential to bring together science, society and policy makers in an impactful way. As a core dimension of Open Science, it opens up the opportunity for all members of society to take an active role in research, innovation and the development of evidence-based policy, at local, national and EU levels.

It is the ambition of the EU-Citizen.Science project ('the Project') to build on the growing impact of citizens participating in research across the full range of scientific enquiry, by developing a sustainable platform to act as a mutual learning space for CS, focusing on Europe, but relevant globally. The overall vision for the EU-Citizen.Science platform ('the Platform') is to aid the mainstreaming of CS in Europe, such that it becomes an appreciated and widely established means for the democratisation of science in Europe, as shown in Figure 1 below.

The building of the Platform is being pursued through three interconnected lines of activity:

1. Coordinating CS actions, and making use of existing resources in the presently fragmented citizen science landscape in Europe,
2. Engaging quadruple helix stakeholders at local, national and European levels, and

3. Creating a mutual learning space and a set of comprehensive, co-designed training modules for different target audiences.

In keeping with our mission, we aim to engage equally with CS participants, practitioners, researchers, policy makers and society throughout the course of the project. In order to do so effectively, it is therefore necessary to have a clear view of our stakeholders - both in the success of the project, and the usefulness of the platform itself.

Figure 1: The Vision, Mission and Objectives of the EU-Citizen.Science project

1.2. Purpose of this deliverable

The fifth work package within the Project (*WP5: Training Needs Assessment, Creation and Delivery*) is focused on creating appropriate training modules for the platform. The second Task 5.2 ‘*Design of tools and resources to curate and host training material and module*’ is focused on:

“Based on the emerging insights from WP2, WP3, and WP4, and the lessons from Tasks 5.1 and 3.1, a user-centred organisation of training material and resources will be set for the EU-Citizen.Science platform. The mapping will consider multiple factors in a typology, including the domain of the scientific activity (e.g. astronomy or biodiversity monitoring), type of engagement (elaborate or opportunistic), language, contribution to SDGs, etc. These factors will be used to classify and organise the material that was collated during Task 5.1. Special attention and close collaboration with Task 3.3 will ensure no duplication of efforts between these tasks. Each resource and piece of information will be associated with metadata that will allow it to be searched and retrieved using the ontological

classification from WP2. During the organisation process, gaps will be identified in terms of material that need further development or does not exist (e.g. training of community scientists). Translation of critical training material to multiple European languages will be directed to the European Citizen Science Translation Hub from the DITOs project. The output of this task will be at least 150 training resources linked and organised on the platform, and a report of the classification and catalogue of the resources that have been identified.”

To address this task, this deliverable (D5.2) presents:

- a) An updated analysis of training and educational material needs (updated since D5.1) based on feedback from an online survey and a workshop with project partners.
- b) A description of the metadata requirements for organising the training and education material on the EU-Citizen.Science platform.
- c) Guidelines, technical- and content-wise, on how to create a module for the EU-Citizen.Science project partners using Moodle. Guidelines on content are based on existing best practice guidelines.

2. Training & Educational Material needs

2.1. Introduction

2.1.1. Training & Educational Material - a definition

With the first release of the EU-Citizen.Science platform, training resources were categorised under the Resources section along with ‘tools’, ‘guidelines’, ‘reports’ and ‘websites’. With the next release of the platform, training resources will have their own section and system for classifying and organising material. Furthermore, training resources will now be referred to as **Training & Educational Material** which is defined as:

Material that is designed or can be used explicitly for the goals of teaching or training a person on the practice of citizen science e.g. how to design and implement a volunteer-based activity, how to control data quality, the ethical and legal requirements of working with volunteers and managing their data. These can include massive open online courses (MOOCs), workshops, webinars, gamified training, and quizzes.

It is important to note that at the present time the Training & Educational Material section of the website will be solely reserved for material that is about the design and implementation of citizen science as a practice and not for very specific activities such as how to carry out a soil survey or how to identify marine fish.

2.1.2. An update on Training & Educational Material needs since D5.1

Here in D5.2 we provide an advanced assessment of the training and educational needs analysis carried out in D5.2 for the following reasons:

- additional data for the Training & Educational Material needs analysis was sourced from a workshop with the EU-Citizen.Science project partners who have a wide-ranging knowledge of the current European CS landscape through their past and/or current participation in a range of European Commission-funded projects on CS (see section 2.2.2 for more information);
- since the publication of D5.1 the coordinators of WP3 have undertaken a needs analysis for Resources and the decision was taken to align the vocabulary used to describe the themes for both Resources and Training & Educational Material, as this new vocabulary better reflects the terminology used more widely throughout the community.

2.2. Methodology

2.2.1. Survey of Training & Educational Material needs

Our initial research into the training needs of our stakeholders came from a survey carried out in August 2019. More details can be found in section 2.2.1 of D5.1, Report on Training Needs. In summary, a survey was circulated to as many key stakeholders as possible of the EU-Citizen.Science project. Stakeholders could be producers or consumers (or both) of CS; they include academic researchers, educators, the press and media, policy makers and civil servants, non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and civil-society organisations (CSOs), industry and small or medium-sized enterprise (SMEs) and, the general public.

The survey was sent to a variety of CS-related academic and press-related mailing lists and also to some more informal areas such as social media and CS-based Facebook groups. Its purpose was threefold: 1) to generate a list of already existing training and educational material, plus tools, guidelines and materials related to CS, the latter of which is the main task of WP3; 2) to identify what training is still needed and 3) to identify priority audiences to target.

The focus of the needs analysis in this deliverable is to address point two and three. The results of point one have led to the creation of several resources relating both to training and education and to tools, guidelines and materials on the EU-Citizen.Science platform.

2.2.2. Workshop with the EU-Citizen.Science project partners

On the 19th of June 2020 we carried out an online workshop with the EU-Citizen.Science project partners (35 individuals from 10 different countries) in which we asked them to:

- Task A: Describe their experience of self-directed learning
- Task B: Come up with an idea for a training module

The workshop was designed to capture feedback from a range of key stakeholders who have a wide-ranging knowledge of the current European CS landscape through their past and/or current participation in a range of European Commission-funded projects on citizen science.

For Task A, participants were asked:

- Question One: Have you ever done a self-directed course, i.e. without a tutor and with automatic marking? What was the subject?
- Question Two: What is a good thing that you can share about self-directed learning? What is the best practice?
- Question Three: What is a bad thing that you can share about self-directed learning? What could have been done better?

For Task B, participants were asked:

- Question One: What is the training module about, and what is the gap?
- Question Two: What is the main audience? (journalists, public, decision makers, scientists)
- Question Three: What is the main content of the module?
- Question Four: What are the activities that the students will take during the learning session? Why?
- Question Five: Other comments:

More details of this workshop and the results from Task A can be found in section 4.3, “Best practice for creating online learning content: feedback from the Consortium.” The results from Task B, in which we discuss potential future modules, are discussed in section 2.4.1, “Training & Educational Material needs - themes”.

2.2.3. Training & Educational Material needs analysis

Data for the Training & Education Material needs analysis was obtained from:

- Question three of the online survey (“In your opinion, what kinds of new training resources are needed in Citizen Science? Please be as specific as you can in terms of training topics or skills and the format in which you would want to access this in (text, video, podcast etc)”).
- Question One, Two and Three of Task B from the workshop with EU-Citizen.Science project partners.

Using the approach described in section 2.2.1 of D3.2 we carried out a thematic analysis of the responses to cluster them according to Theme, Audience, Domain of Scientific Activity and Material Format and Type.

2.3. Overview of the training material currently available on the EU-Citizen.Science platform

Section 3.2 of deliverable 3.2 provides an overview of the material available on the EU-Citizen.Science platform on the 14th of July 2020. At the time of analysis, of the 82 resources available 13 were Training & Educational Materials. The 13 materials were clustered into themes that were identified in D3.2 and are defined in Appendix 1 of this deliverable. The existing materials on the platform cover 17 themes (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Themes that describe the 13 training materials available on the EU-Citizen.Science platform on the 14th of July 2020. Note that training materials could be assigned to multiple themes.

2.4. Training & Educational Material needs results

Four distinguishing descriptors emerged from the analysis in which respondents described the Training & Educational Material:

- **Themes:** specifies a topic within CS (e.g., engagement, data quality and standards, regulations and ethics).
- **Audience:** specifies the type of audience that the training material should cater for (e.g. policy makers, citizen science practitioners).
- **Domain of Scientific Activity:** specifies the field or discipline that the material relates to (e.g. Astronomy, Education, Ecology and Environment).
- **Format & Type:** specifies the format (e.g. lecture, MOOC, handout) and type (e.g. Text, Moving Image) of the material.

2.4.1. Training & Educational Material needs - themes

Respondents' descriptions of Training & Educational Material requirements could be assigned to one of the 19 themes described in Appendix 1. These themes were developed according to the thematic analysis of both Training & Educational Material and Resources presented in D3.2. Across both the online survey and the project partner workshop, a total of 106 requests were made for material covering 15 different themes (Figure 3) but with multiple requests for nine of these (Table 1). The most frequent requests for material were on the following themes (Figure 3):

- An introduction to CS
- Research design and methods
- Engagement
- Data quality and standards
- Transferability
- Communication

Figure 3: Themes of the Training & Educational Material requests from the online survey and workshop.

Table 1: The specific topics respondents described (during the online survey and the partner workshop) that were classified under each theme. Topics in **bold** were mentioned more than once.

Training & Educational Material Theme	Specific topic(s)
Co-creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How to co-design projects - Technology co-creation

<p>Communication</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training for scientists and practitioners on how to make academic-style data presentation engaging for a non-specialist audience - Training for scientists and practitioners on the presentation of subject data and how this impacts data quality - Training for scientists and CS practitioners on results communication between researchers and citizen scientists - Feedback to volunteers - Communication with citizens - Tools for communication - Training focused on communication - Training for citizens on how to publish research results in academic publications
<p>Data quality and standards</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training for scientists and CS practitioners on how to create projects with high quality data - Training for scientists and CS practitioners on maximising data quality adequate for academic publication - Training for scientists, citizens and CS practitioners on better understanding data and the importance of null values. - Data reliability - Training for scientists and CS practitioners on tools, methods, stats and data techniques for quality assurance - Training for citizens on data quality - Training for scientists and CS practitioners on techniques for handling unstructured data and obtaining robust conclusions - Training for citizens and CS practitioners on an overview of research design and methods, data quality and standards
<p>Empowerment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CS and activism - CS and social justice
<p>Engagement</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Feedback/ communication with volunteers - Involvement of under-represented audiences - Training for scientists on how to work with volunteers and how to carry out recruitment - Training for citizens wishing to start a project - Training for all audiences on how to keep volunteers engaged - Tools for communication - How to plan/ organise/ manage training for citizen scientists
<p>Evaluation of CS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Appropriate metrics for evaluating CS impacts (particularly societal) and how to measure
<p>Impact</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How to reach decision makers and design projects in a way that they can have policy impact

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - History and impact of citizen science and how to create an impactful project - Training on the impacts of CS - Appropriate metrics for evaluating CS impacts (particularly societal) and how to measure
Instructables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training for scientists and practitioners on how to start up a wildlife recording citizen science project - Training for scientists on how to use CS in health research - Training for scientists and practitioners on how to create a training video for a CS project - Training for scientists and practitioners on how to create an impactful project
Introduction to CS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training for scientists on the benefits of citizen science - Training for scientists on an introduction to citizen science and themes of interest - Training that showcases the variety and applications of CS - An introduction to CS for citizens - An introduction to CS for policy-makers - An introduction to CS for funders - Resources that allow citizen scientists to develop their own projects - Training for scientists on the history and impact of citizen science - The basics of designing a CS project for scientists - Training for CS practitioners on the concept of CS, communication channels, recruiting volunteers, data management
Link with formal education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training for teachers on how to use CS in schools - CS training resources for schools - The applications of CS in schools designed for all audiences - Training for all audiences on how to merge CS research with the curriculum
Project management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training for scientists and practitioners on volunteer management - Training for CS practitioners on project management - Training for citizens on the basics of running a project - Sustaining long-term projects (the funding, organisational and practical aspects)
Project sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustaining long-term projects (the funding, organisational and practical aspects) - Training for CS practitioners and scientists on how to think about a project beyond a single-funding cycle - Training for policy-makers and funders on the funding aspects of CS
Regulations and ethics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training for scientists and CS practitioners on how to handle private data

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training on the ethics and legal matters, particularly with regards to working with children - Challenges in managing the ethics of CS and how to tackle them - Training for scientists, CS practitioners, citizens, funders and policy-makers on the ethics and legal considerations of data sharing - Training for scientists and CS practitioners on the ethics and legal considerations of CS
Research design and methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training for scientists and CS practitioners on structuring the analysis task and methods to improve data quality - A basic introduction on the methods for scientific investigation - Training on research design and suitable methods in an accessible format - Training on scientific questioning - Training on participative methods - Training on how to define a research question - Training for citizens on how to design a CS project - Training on how to run a workshop - Training for scientists and CS practitioners on how to create a training video for a CS project - Training for citizen scientists and CS practitioners on research design and methods, and data quality
Transferability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How to transfer research into a CS context for scientists and CS practitioners - Applications of AI in CS - Training for scientists and CS practitioners on new methods for CS (bottom-up led) - CS in museums - Transferability of CS to other potential domains (e.g. language learning and teaching) and scientific disciplines - Training on how CS could contribute to SDG monitoring and implementation - Training for - Domain-specific training material - Training for scientists on how to apply CS to health research - Training for all audiences on how to merge CS research with the curriculum

2.4.2. Training & Educational Material needs - audience

In many cases the audience type for a theme was not specified (Table 2). Where audience was specified the most frequent requests were as follows:

- An introduction to citizen scientists for scientists and CS practitioners
- Data quality and standards for scientists, CS practitioners and citizens
- Engagement for scientists and CS practitioners
- Research design and methods for scientists, CS practitioners and citizens

The results of this updated analysis mirror the earlier analysis in D5.1 with a greater number of requests for material for the researcher/scientist and CS practitioner communities than for other groups. The lack of requests may not in fact be indicative of the importance or the order with which audiences should be prioritised but may in fact reflect the make-up of the audience. Many of the themes and audiences that were frequently requested may in part reflect the audience demographics and so in future surveys it would be interesting to capture information on how the respondents would prioritise these themes. Similarly, we would also stress the importance of re-evaluating the communities needs in the near future: it is inevitable, with the rapid evolution of the CS landscape that new themes and topics are likely to emerge.

Table 2: The frequency with which particular themes were requested by respondents according to the audience type (R/S=Researchers / scientists, CS P=Citizen science practitioners, C=Citizens, T=Teachers, F=Funders, PM=Policy makers, NS=Not specified). Adapted from D3.2.

Themes / Audience	R/S	CS P	C	T	F	PM	NS
Co-creation							2
Communication	4	4	1				
Data quality and standards	7	7	3				4
Empowerment			1				1
Volunteer engagement	6	5	1				5
Evaluation of citizen science	1	1					1
Impact	1	1					3
Innovation	1	1					
Instructables	4	3					
Introduction to CS	6	4	2		1	1	2
Link with formal education	2	2	1	4	1	1	
Project management	1	2	1				1
Project sustainability	1	1			1	1	1
Regulations and ethics	3	3					2
Research design and methods	2	3	3				9
Transferability	5	5	2		1	1	4

2.4.3. Training & Educational Material needs - format and type

The responses (Figure 4) to the question on format preferences for new training and educational material demonstrate that respondents were describing two separate things and so some of the items were not necessarily mutually exclusive (e.g. Text and Handbook):

- Material Format (hereafter referred to as ‘Resource Format’ in keeping with the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative vocabulary which is presented in Table 6 of section 3.1.5): this identifies the genre of the material/ resource e.g. moving image, text, event.
- Material Type (hereafter referred to as ‘Learning Resource Type’ in keeping with the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative vocabulary which is presented in Table 6 of section 3.1.5): this field specifies the type of Resource Format e.g. video, journal article, face-to-face workshop.

However, we have presented the respondents requests for the resource formats and types to inform the vocabulary for the search facility (metadata) for the platform. These are discussed in more detail in section 3.1.5.

Two further requests were made by questionnaire participants which do not strictly qualify as formats, but which are worth a mention. The first was for material to be made available in a multitude of languages. This is already planned and will be developed with the aid of the CS Translation Hub (see section 5.2.2 of D3.2). The EU-Citizen.Science platform already states the language of each resource, and there are plans to make resources available on the Citizen Science Translation Hub for translation.

The second request of this type was for in-person training or events. This request was independently made by two people. By definition the EU-Citizen.Science platform is online and cannot offer in-person training; but it was something that was wished for - and something regularly provided by the earlier project “Doing It Together Science” (DITOs), which ran 500 CS events and whose social media channels were handed on to EU-Citizen.Science. DITOs demonstrated the value of face-to-face events, and there is potential for EU-Citizen.Science to at least provide an events page alerting visitors to face-to-face events taking place near them, even if EU-Citizen.Science itself does not provide events.

Figure 4: Formats and types of training and educational material requested by respondents to the online survey (question three) and workshop.

2.4.4. Training & Education Material needs - domain of scientific activity

Unfortunately, the online survey and workshop questions were not designed to capture information on the domain of the scientific activity (e.g. ecology and environment, health sciences) contained in the training material. For that reason, and because it was so infrequently mentioned, we have not presented a detailed analysis of the responses. However, we would recommend that it is included within the metadata requirements to aid search functionality on the platform. Until a vocabulary can be defined according to user requests, we recommend using the Public Participation in Scientific Research (PPSR) metadata standard vocabulary for Science Topic which is designed for CS projects and is currently used for Topic for the Projects section of the platform. However, to improve the search options with future releases of the platform we recommend undertaking usability tests with a variety of audiences to better understand their search requirements.

3. Training & Educational Material - metadata requirements

3.1. Introduction

3.1.1. Best practice in metadata and ontologies

Metadata is “data that provides information about other data”¹ and is crucial to aiding the discovery and identification of content on the Platform. Descriptive metadata is information about a resource, such as its title, author, and keywords to describe the content. Metadata enrich the content available on the platform by providing as much useful information as possible, contribute to a well-structured Information Architecture and data layer for the platform, and aid search for the user.

An ontology is a “a set of concepts and categories in a subject area or domain that shows their properties and the relations between them”² that are the subject of the metadata, i.e. the CS resources and platforms to be shared on the Platform. The goal of having ontologies is to reduce complexity and organise information into a system of categories according to terminology that have been agreed upon within that field, so that data and knowledge are more easily shared.

A controlled vocabulary is a list of terms that have been enumerated explicitly for use in a specific data field. This list is controlled by and is available from a controlled vocabulary registration authority as Schema.org³, PPSR⁴, or Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI)⁵. All terms in a controlled vocabulary should have an unambiguous, non-redundant definition. A controlled vocabulary may have no meaning specified, it can also just be a set of terms that people agree to use, and their meaning is understood, or it may have very detailed definitions for each term.

In this way, the ontologies and vocabularies the Project applies will inform the content of the metadata, the keywords & tags, and the information hierarchy of the Platform. The main ontology components relevant to the Platform are *class* ontologies (the types of resources) and *attribute* ontologies (the aspects, properties, features, and characteristics of the CS resources shared and the CS projects profiled).

For the description of the CS Projects profiled on the Platform, we are following the PPSR-Common Conceptual Model, which consists of the Project Metadata Model (PMM), Dataset Metadata Model

¹ <https://www.iab.com/insights/>

² <https://languages.oup.com/google-dictionary-en/>

³ <https://schema.org/>

⁴ <https://www.wilsoncenter.org/article/ppsr-core-metadata-standards>

⁵ <https://www.dublincore.org/>

(DMM) and Observation Data Model (ODM). More information about PPSR Core can be found on CitSci.org⁶ (one of the founding members) and in the PPSR Core GitHub repository⁷.

As the project progresses, we are making successive improvements with respect to the metadata selection, with the primary aim of ensuring compatibility with the PPSR metadata standard, and interoperability globally.

3.1.2. Metadata for describing Citizen Science Resources in general

Because there is no metadata standard for describing CS resources, the first release of the EU-Citizen.Science platform used the ontology proposed by Schema.org on Digital Document (and a small variation for Courses). Schema.org vocabulary can be used with many different encodings, including RDFa, Microdata and JSON-LD. These vocabularies cover entities, relationships between entities and actions, and can easily be extended through a well-documented extension model. Over 10 million sites use Schema.org to markup their web pages and email messages.

Founded by Google, Microsoft, Yahoo and Yandex, Schema.org vocabularies are developed by an open community process, using the public-schemaorg@w3.org mailing list and through GitHub. Using this schema within the Information Architecture of the Platform enhances the interoperability of the Platform with other such platforms and resources, and any future potential linked data cloud or Semantic Web implementations. These standards are maintained by the Schema.org initiative. Within these, the Resource Description Framework (RDF) is a specification developed and maintained under the auspices of the W3C, and is maintained at <http://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema/>. The RDF schema provides mechanisms for describing groups of related resources and the relationships between these resources.

For the first release of the Platform, the following metadata (shown in Table 3 below) were developed together with all other Work Packages (WPs) of the project, especially with WP3. For resources we are following the metadata proposed by schema.org for digital documents.

Table 3: List of Metadata for Resources.

Metadata for Resources		
Property	Expected Type	Description

⁶ https://www.citsci.org/CWIS438/Websites/CitSci/PPSR_CORE_Documentation.php?WebSiteID=7

⁷ <https://github.com/CitSciAssoc/DMWG-PPSR-Core>

Properties from CreativeWork⁸		
about	thing	The subject matter of the content. Inverse property: subjectOf.
abstract	Text	An abstract is a short description that summarises a CreativeWork.
aggregateRating	AggregateRating	The overall rating, based on a collection of reviews or ratings, of the item.
audience	Audience	An intended audience, i.e. a group for whom something was created. Supersedes serviceAudience.
author	Organisation or Person	The author of this content or rating. Please note that author is special in that HTML 5 provides a special mechanism for indicating authorship via the rel tag. That is equivalent to this and may be used interchangeably.
datePublished	Date	Date of first broadcast/publication.
inLanguage	Language or Text	The language of the content or performance or used in an action. Please use one of the language codes from the IETF BCP 47 standard. See also availableLanguage. Supersedes language.
keywords	Text	Keywords or tags used to describe this content. Multiple entries in a keywords list are typically delimited by commas.
license	CreativeWork or URL	A license document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL.
publisher	Organisation or	The publisher of the creative work.

⁸ CreativeWork is an item from schema.org. Each item in the vocabulary has a set of properties. New items can be created on top of others (for example, Digital Document is built on top of CreativeWork which is built on top of Thing). In this way, some of the Resources properties are inherited from CreativeWork and other properties are inherited from Thing. On the other hand, the Expected Type can be a Text, but also an Item (e.g. Thing), so this field is expected to have one or more of the properties of this type.

	Person	
Properties from Thing		
image	imageObject or URL	An image of the item. This can be a URL or a fully described ImageObject.
name	Text	The name of the item
url	URL	URL of the item

3.1.3. Resource Type Categories used in the First Release

The resource categories used in the first release of the platform were developed as part of the work undertaken in WP3 to develop quality criteria for the resources shared on the platform.

These categories are as follows:

- *Guidelines* are written texts such as reports, deliverables, or briefings that describe best practices or provide instructions that can be helpful in designing, implementing or evaluating CS or initiatives relevant to CS.
- *Scientific publications* are peer-reviewed texts about CS, ideally sharing practical experience, knowledge, and recommendations for initiating or running CS projects.
- *Reports* are documents that present information on CS or on topics relevant to CS.
- *Websites* and webpages are online sites where CS related guidance, experience, and knowledge is published and shared.
- *Training resources* are designed or can be used explicitly for the goals of teaching or training a person e.g. instructional materials about how to complete a CS task, or how to initiate and run a CS project, and can include massive open online courses (MOOCs), workshops, webinars, gamified training, and quizzes.
- *Tools* are software (including apps and web platforms) or hardware that support a particular task in CS initiatives, such as water quality equipment, air quality sensors, etc.
- *Libraries* are organised sets of technical resources such as databases, repositories, toolkits and toolboxes that bring together relevant documents for a particular purpose in CS initiatives.
- *Audio resources* are sound files with CS related content such as podcasts, audio books, radio broadcasts, etc.
- *Visual resources* are visual content related to CS such as videos, diagrams, figures, illustrations, etc.

These categories have enabled us to develop resource quality criteria that directly relate to each type of resource, such as legibility and a good structure for text documents, and good video and audio quality

for video resources. These are described in greater detail in the Framework Report Describing Criteria and Rationale for Sharing and Selecting State of the art Citizen Science Resources⁹.

However, now that we are seeking collaborations with other platforms to share data via APIs, and have the clear mandate to be as globally interoperable as possible, we are now introducing an established universal metadata standard for describing resource types. This will have the additional benefit of improving the function to search for resources on the platform as well as enabling future platform collaborations.

3.1.4. New Resource Type Categories

In order to follow a more universally recognised standard for describing types of resources, we turn to the Dublin Core schema, which was specifically developed for describing digital resources, physical resources such as books or CDs, and objects like artworks¹⁰. The DCMI Type Vocabulary¹¹ provides a general, cross-domain list of approved terms that may be used as values for the Resource Type element to identify the genre of a resource. The terms documented here are also included in the more comprehensive document ‘DCMI Metadata Terms’¹².

The Resource Type categories are:

- Collection
- Dataset
- Event
- Image
- Interactive Resource (Website)
- Moving Image (Video)
- Physical Object (Hardware)
- Service
- Software
- Sound
- Still Image
- Text

The ‘Image’ type includes both ‘Moving Image’ and ‘Still Image’ types - *“A visual representation other than text. Examples include images and photographs of physical objects, paintings, prints, drawings,*

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/record/3716236>

¹⁰ See: <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/usageguide/>

¹¹ <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-type-vocabulary/>

¹² <http://dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/>

other images and graphics, animations and moving pictures, film, diagrams, maps, musical notation. Note that Image may include both electronic and physical representations."¹³

Instead of requiring our users to select Image, and then Still or Moving, we elect to exclude the overarching type of 'Image' and simply list 'Moving Image' and 'Still Image', to avoid confusion and an unnecessary step (having both levels would not aid search results, and having only the lower level will not hinder interoperability).

The resource types currently being used on the website map well against this new resource type vocabulary, allowing the Quality Criteria that have been developed to continue to be applied to the new vocabulary. The one category of resource that will not be continued in the new vocabulary is Training & Educational Material - 'Material that is designed or can be used explicitly for the goals of teaching or training a person e.g. instructional materials about how to complete a citizen science task, or how to initiate and run a citizen science project, and can include massive open online courses (MOOCs), workshops, webinars, gamified training, and quizzes.' This is because Training Resources will now be listed on the EU-Citizen.Science platform in their own content section, such that the next release of the platform will contain CS Projects, CS Resources, and CS Training and Educational Material. The resource type vocabulary will be applied identically to both Resources and Training and Educational Materials.

For the purposes of CS related resources on the platform, the 'Text' category can be broken down further into a range of typical types of text within the context of this field, namely:

- Report
- Project Deliverable
- Guideline
- Policy Brief
- Scientific Publication
- White Paper / Green Paper
- Book
- Other

3.1.5. Metadata for describing Training Materials

As noted above, the second release of the EU-Citizen.Science platform, shared content will be divided into three sections: **Citizen Science Projects**, **Citizen Science Resources**, and **Citizen Science Training and Educational Materials** (the latter of which is a new feature on the platform). Although training materials can be described using the Dublin Core resource type categories outlined above, they also require a range of specific metadata fields that relate more specifically to their educational character

¹³ <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/dcmitype/Image/>

and purpose, such as training videos and Massive Online Open Courses (MOOCs). For this purpose (as also described in the D2.3: Platform Functionality Requirements & Specification Report) we turn to the Course metadata from Schema.org¹⁴, as shown in Table 4 below for the specific description of training materials.

The Schema.org Course metadata are used to describe educational courses, education offered through different media or modes of study, educational events, and/or creative works, which aims to build knowledge, competence or ability of learners.

Table 4. Initial List of Metadata fields for Training and Educational Materials

Metadata for Courses		
Properties from Course		
CoursePrerequisites	AlignmentObject or Course or Text	Requirements for taking the Course. May be completion of another Course or a textual description like "permission of instructor". Requirements may be a prerequisite competency, referenced using AlignmentObject.
Properties from CreativeWork		
about	Thing	The subject matter of the content. Inverse property: subjectOf.
abstract	Text	An abstract is a short description that summarises a CreativeWork.
aggregateRating	AggregateRating	The overall rating, based on a collection of reviews or ratings, of the item.
audience	Audience	An intended audience, i.e. a group for whom something was created. Supersedes serviceAudience.
author	Organisation or Person	The author of this content or rating. Please note that author is special in that HTML 5 provides a special mechanism for indicating authorship via the rel tag. That is equivalent to this and may be used interchangeably.
datePublished	Date	Date of first broadcast/publication.
inLanguage	Language or Text	The language of the content or performance or used

¹⁴ <https://schema.org/Course>

		in an action. Please use one of the language codes from the IETF BCP 47 standard. See also availableLanguage. Supersedes language.
keywords	Text	Keywords or tags used to describe this content. Multiple entries in a keywords list are typically delimited by commas.
license	CreativeWork or URL	A license document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL.
publisher	Organization or Person	The publisher of the creative work.
Properties from Thing		
image	imageObject or URL	An image of the item. This can be a URL or a fully described ImageObject.
name	Text	The name of the item
url	URL	URL of the item

These descriptive fields were used during the WP5 Task 5.1 to collect information on CS training materials, which is now being finalised for inclusion on the next release of the platform. To these predetermined fields, we now add an additional number of fields that will be useful for the users of the platform in search and assessing the training materials for those that best meet their needs and requirements.

Table 5. List of Additional Metadata fields for Training & Educational Materials

Metadata for Courses		
Properties from Course		
educationalLevel	DefinedTerm or Text or URL	The level in terms of progression through an educational or training context. Examples of educational levels include 'beginner', 'intermediate' or 'advanced', and formal sets of level indicators
learningResourceType	Text	The predominant type or kind characterising the learning resource. For example, 'presentation', 'handout'.

timeRequired	Duration	Approximate or typical time it takes to work with or through this learning resource for the typical intended target audience, e.g. 'PT30M', 'PT1H25M'. Typical time of lesson
ConditionsOfAccess	Text	Conditions that affect the availability of, or method(s) of access to, an item. Typically used for real world items such as an ArchiveComponent held by an ArchiveOrganization. This property is not suitable for use as a general Web access control mechanism. It is expressed only in natural language. For example "Available by appointment from the Reading Room" or "Accessible only from logged-in accounts".

We now pull these together for the definitive metadata profile for CS Training and Educational Resources on the EU-Citizen.Science Platform, together with the information that will be provided on the platform for these data fields. This table will inform the development of the Training Material profiles on the platform, and the form for users to add their own Training Materials.

Table 6. Final metadata fields for training and educational materials

Mandatory Information				
Field Name	Schema / DCMI term	Data type	Description from Schema / DCMI	EU-Citizen.Science Description
Title	name	Text	The name of the item	The title of the training material
Description	abstract	Text	An abstract is a short description that summarises a CreativeWork.	Describe the training material in approximately 500 words
Keywords	keywords	Text	Keywords or tags used to describe this content. Multiple entries in a keywords list are typically delimited by commas.	Please provide additional keywords to describe this training material. Place a comma after the word to add new keywords.
Resource Format	resourceType	Vocabulary: Collection Dataset Event	The DCMI Type Vocabulary provides a general, cross-domain list of approved terms that	Please select the format (resource type) of the training material

		<p>Interactive Resource (Website)</p> <p>Moving Image (Video)</p> <p>Physical Object (Hardware)</p> <p>Service</p> <p>Software</p> <p>Sound</p> <p>Still Image</p> <p>Text:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Report -Deliverable -Guideline -Scientific Publication -Book -Other 	<p>may be used as values for the Resource Type element to identify the genre of a resource</p>	
Learning Resource Type	learningResourceType	Text	<p>The predominant type or kind characterizing the learning resource. For example, 'presentation', 'handout'.</p>	<p>Please indicate the type of learning material, such as MOOC, lesson plan, learning activity, lecture, handout, etc</p>
Theme		<p>Vocabulary:</p> <p>Introduction to CS</p> <p>Best practices</p> <p>Project management</p> <p>Research design and methods</p> <p>Engagement</p> <p>Co-creation</p> <p>Communication</p> <p>Event planning</p> <p>CS stories</p> <p>Empowerment</p> <p>Data quality and standards</p> <p>Instructions</p> <p>Link with formal education</p> <p>Regulations and</p>		<p>Please select one or more themes directly addressed by the training material</p>

		ethics Impact Evaluation of citizen science Project sustainability Transferability Reflections on science Other Not Applicable		
Topic	projectScienceType	Vocabulary: Update from latest PPSR Vocab + Citizen Science Open Science RRI Other Not Applicable	PPSR: “This current list represents an aggregation of terms from existing implementations and does not yet comply with the guidelines for mutual exclusivity and non-ambiguity. It is also known to be incomplete in terms of full representation/ coverage of areas of science and is therefore likely to change over time. Implementations should be mindful of this and should engage actively with the PPSR-Core community to monitor changes and contribute to the discussion.”	Please select one or more topics directly addressed by the training material
Keywords	keywords	Text	Keywords or tags used to describe this content. Multiple entries in a keywords list are typically delimited by commas.	Please provide additional keywords to describe this training material, such as ‘Volunteer Management’ or ‘Train the Trainer’. Place a comma after the keyword to add new keywords.
URL	url	URL	URL of the item	The url at which the training material can be found or accessed
Language	inLanguage	Language or Text	The language of the	The language of the training

			content or performance or used in an action. Please use one of the language codes from the IETF BCP 47 standard. See also availableLanguage. Supersedes language.	material.
Publisher	publisher	Organisation or Person	The publisher of the creative work.	Please indicate the publisher of the training material, such as University, Organisation, Project Name, or Person
Audience	audience	Vocabulary: Researchers & Academics Educators Community Members & Citizens CS Project Leaders & Initiators CSOs & NGOs Policy & Decision Makers ALL Audiences	An intended audience, i.e. a group for whom something was created. Supersedes serviceAudience	
Image	image	imageObject or URL	An image of the item. This can be a URL or a fully described ImageObject.	Please provide an image that can be used to illustrate the training material profile on the platform.

Where possible, please provide the following additional information

Field Name	Schema / DCMI term	Data type	Description from Schema / DCMI	EU-Citizen.Science Description
Conditions of Access	conditionsofAccess	text	Conditions that affect the availability of, or method(s) of access to, an item. Typically used for real world items such as an ArchiveComponent ¹⁵ held by an ArchiveOrganization ¹⁶ .	Please describe any conditions that affect the accessibility of the training material, such as 'requires registration', 'requires enrollment', or 'requires payment'.

¹⁵ <https://schema.org/ArchiveComponent>

¹⁶ <https://schema.org/ArchiveOrganization>

			<p>This property is not suitable for use as a general Web access control mechanism. It is expressed only in natural language.</p> <p>For example "Available by appointment from the Reading Room" or "Accessible only from logged-in accounts".</p>	
Time Required	timeRequired	Text	<p>Approximate or typical time it takes to work with or through this learning resource for the typical intended target audience, e.g. 'PT30M', 'PT1H25M'.</p>	<p>Please indicate the typical amount of time it will take to complete the use of this training material. For example, a part-time two week course, a one-hour video, or 25 minute quiz.</p>
Educational Level	educationalLevel	Text	<p>The level in terms of progression through an educational or training context. Examples of educational levels include 'beginner', 'intermediate' or 'advanced', and formal sets of level indicators.</p>	<p>Please indicate the level in terms of progression through an educational or training context, such as 'beginner', 'intermediate' or 'advanced'; and 'primary', 'secondary', or 'University'.</p>
Date Published	datePublished	Date	<p>Date of first broadcast/publication.</p>	<p>Please provide the date that the training material was first created, published, or delivered</p>
License	license	Text or URL	<p>A license document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL.</p>	<p>Please provide any information regarding the content licence, such as 'Creative Commons zero (CC 0)', 'Creative Commons Attribution (4.0) International (CC-BY 4.0)', 'Creative Commons Attribution Noncommercial (CC-BY-NC)', 'Creative Commons Attribution Share Alike (CC-BY-SA)', or 'Creative Commons Attribution Noncommercial Share Alike (CC-BY-NC-</p>

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4. Guidelines for creating a training and educational module for the EU-Citizen.Science platform

The training modules on the EU-Citizen.Science platform will be developed using the Moodle learning management system¹⁷. In this section, we provide the guidance on setting up a unit using the system, and the process of designing the content.

4.1. Technical - how to set up a course on Moodle

To familiarise yourself with the platform and method, we recommend that course administrators watch the YouTube video “How can I create a course on Moodle?” at https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=G11YAI Du_mc.

The setting up of a new training module requires administrative access to Moodle. Under “Site administration” (See Figure 5), choose the “Courses” tab, and then “Add a new course”. (The Moodle site will refer to modules as “courses”. The two terms will mean the same thing in this document.)

Site administration

Figure 5: Site Administration Interface.

4.1.1. General

For each course, provide the following details: “Course full name” and “course short name” in the first two boxes. Choose a course category (beginner, intermediary, and advanced) but leave the visibility on “hide” until the course is ready. The “course start date” can be the official release date of the course,

¹⁷ <https://moodle.org/>

though of course students may begin any time after this. Ensure that the course end date is disabled by unticking the “Enable” box after “Course End Date”.

4.1.2. Description

There will be a large textbox for a detailed course description. This will affect the courses’s SEO, so please start the opening with “This is a free and open course of X [usually 1-2] hours”, then explain the significance of the course and why the learner should take it, and then the topics that are covered in the course. For “course image”, use an image size of 500 x 500 to represent the unit.

4.1.3. Course format

Select the “Topics” format in the first drop-down menu, and, in coordination with the course designer, set the appropriate number of sections. This number is usually between 8 and 12. Of these, there will always be sections for “Welcome and introduction”, “Conclusion and self-assessment”, “further information and learning” and “sources and acknowledgement” and at least four sections of the module itself.

For “course layout”, in EU-Citizen.Science we will always use “show all sections on one page” .

4.1.4. Appearance

The options here are currently left up to the training provider to decide. We recommend “do not force language”.

4.1.5. Files and Uploads

This section allows us to set limits on the size of files that may be uploaded. We will not be expecting students to upload files of their own, but course administrators may wish to upload several items. We encourage course administrators to use a variety of media, e.g. videos, pictures, graphs, animations, quizzes, etc. At present, we anticipate that leaving the size limit for uploads is left as the site default. This can be altered if any problems occur (e.g. many or large files slowing down the Moodle site).

4.1.6. Completion tracking

Under this heading, ensure that it is enabled (choose “yes” in the drop-down menu).

4.1.7. Groups

As these modules will be carried out by individuals alone and without a tutor, please choose “no” for all the options under this heading.

4.1.8. Role renaming

Unless you have a particular requirement for your course, please leave these fields blank.

4.1.9. Tags

There will be a text box saying “Enter tags” which you can use like a free text box. The tags will appear above the box once you press “Enter”. A standard EU-Citizen.Science list of tags will be created, e.g. “citizen science”, “volunteer management”, “policy”, etc. but you will be free to add your own for a more specialist course.

One box will be called “Course ID number”. It has not yet been decided how to assign course numbers; this will be the subject of future discussion as we create our first ten modules. This guide will be updated when a decision is made.

Please click “save and display”.

4.1.10. Participants

You will next be asked about “enrollments”. You will need to enrol yourself or another agreed person as a course manager. Their name and e-mail address should automatically appear when you click the grey “enrol users” button on the right.

Students should be able to self-enrol. If the option to allow self-enrolment is not visible, please see the guidance in the section “Uploading material to Moodle” (page 44).

4.1.11. Course badges

The next stage is to add a badge for the course. This is done under the “site administration” tab, and “add a new badge”. Alternatively, when you click on a course, you will see the name of your course, “participants” under that, then “badges”.

You will need to choose an image to create the badge and a badge name. ECSA is expected to design its own badges; they will work best as JPEG or similar files. If you choose a different one, please ensure that it is not a copyrighted image. If it is your own artwork, please decide on what kind of license you wish to attach to it (e.g. creative commons).

A single glossary of terms will be developed that will apply to all courses. We will encourage our students to highlight any words they feel should be in it.

4.2. Content design - how to design an online course for Moodle

The process of developing content for an online course without an instructor is a task that requires significant attention and time investment. The design and development of your course’s content will take about 10-20 hours for each hour of training material that is displayed online.

The conditions under which the training modules of EU-Citizen.Science need to operate are the most challenging for online learning - they are intended for a learner who cannot benefit from a cohort of other learners who start the unit at the same time or from the availability of an instructor who can answer questions and help clarify different issues. Therefore, modules - and each section of them - need to be engaging and interesting, while also providing up-to-date and useful information for the learner. Because of these conditions, it is critical that you carefully plan and design your module well before any material is developed.

In this section, we will guide you through the core principles of preparing material to the EU-Citizen.Science platform. The information here is based on UCL Connected Learning material, and more heavily on the UK Open University OpenLearnCreate course “How to make an open online course”. We highly recommend that you take this course¹⁸. Additionally, you might want to refer to UCL’s Connected Learning material¹⁹ and Coursera²⁰.

For the training and educational modules, the EU-Citizen.Science platform has an extensive template for designing a course (see Appendix 3). Please always fill it in and use it for the planning. The template is provided with partial design, and implementation of a module. Here, we provide guidance on the process of designing a training unit to ensure that minimum quality standards are being kept. Our EU-Citizen.Science modules should be designed for 1 to 2 hours of self-directed learning, as described on Page 25 of the project’s DoA. The aim here is to provide modules that can fit into many people’s schedules and time constraints and fill a gap in the training and education for CS.

When designing a module, please start with a course description and the learning objectives and outcomes, and the main division of the course. Learning objectives describe the *purpose* of the course, while learning outcomes state *what the student should be able to do at the end* and are usually measurable outcomes that can be linked to evaluation. Of these tasks, the most important are the design and the writing of the learning objectives or outcomes. Learning objectives and outcomes are about the expectation of what the learner should know and be able to do at the end of a unit. They are frequently described using Bloom’s taxonomy of learning²¹ which include: knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation. As the units will be short and without the opportunity for the marking of essays, it is most likely that our assessments will focus on knowledge and comprehension. For learning objectives, see Writing Good Learning Outcomes by University of California, Davis²² and for a good vocabulary of learning objectives see the end of

¹⁸ <https://www.open.edu/openlearncreate/local/ocwcreatecourse/gettingstarted.php>

¹⁹ <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/teaching-learning/publications/2020/may/ucl-connected-learning-baseline>

²⁰ <https://www.coursera.org/learn/learning-how-to-learn>

²¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bloom%27s_taxonomy

²² <https://canvas.ucdavis.edu/courses/34528/pages/writing-good-learning-outcomes>

Writing and using Learning Outcomes by University of Cardiff²³. An example of a learning objective is:

“By the end of this course, the learner will be able to explain the historical background and current activities in Citizen Science, by identifying key terms and concepts”.

In an EU-Citizen.Science training unit, please aim for 2 or 3 objectives.

The next step in the design is the identification of topics into which the course will be broken. Each training module will have, as a standard, the following core units: “Welcome and introduction”, “Conclusion and self-assessment”, “Further information and learning” and “Sources and acknowledgements”. Between the introduction and conclusion, there should be 4-8 sections. Each section should relate to learning objectives and be clear on what the learner is gaining from it.

Once the section of the module has been identified (description, learning objectives or outcomes, main division), the outline should be peer reviewed by other experts and tested with 3-5 people who belong to the target audience of the module.

The next stage in the design is the development of each section. This should be done using the following approach. For each section, develop a table with the following details:

Table 7: Moodle course content planning.

What?	How?	Why?
1.1 The content or task you’re proposing to include, e.g. Introduction to the course: structure, practical, assignment, reading and use of Moodle (x minutes)	The means by which you aim to deliver it, e.g. a talking head style video of module leader explaining the course’s focus and approach. Be as specific as you can.	Rationale for inclusion, e.g. to situate learners and set expectations for engagement.

Notice the following: in the “what?” column, indicate the cell ID so it can be numbered and checked later, and identify the length of the activity in minutes. This is critical for the appropriate design of the activities.

When planning activities, use granularity of 2-10 minutes. If you are planning to record a lecture or a set of slides, be aware that evidence from online learning shows that the people will not watch long videos, and therefore any video that is integrated as an activity should be up to 5 or 6 minutes. Studies suggest that 2.5 minutes is the optimum. Videos can be “broken down” into sections. The Moodle

²³ <https://www.cardiff.ac.uk/learning-hub/view/writing-and-using-learning-outcomes>

platform contains tools for rich and interactive media presentations (called H5P) and it is recommended to use the capabilities that are offered in it to present various issues.

The standard sections of each course will have the following content, which follows the principle of “tell them what you are going to tell them, tell them, tell them what you told them”:

Welcome and introduction to the course - this section provides an introduction to the module from the course tutor, which must be in video or audio of about 1-2 minutes. It is important that the learners can see a face with a clear indication of who the person (or persons) behind the module is, as this provides credibility and trust. In this section, please include an overview of the content and the learning outcomes. If relevant, provide a teaser and a sample for something that is central to the course so the learner can assess if the course is for them. The introductory text needs to be clear and enticing. When recording the video (or other videos for the course) be aware that audio clarity is key, and that you can use a smartphone quality as long as it is clear.

Summary and self-assessment - summary of the course and end-of-course quiz. The summary should review the topics and highlight the most important “take away” messages. Please also include links to the other final sections, though do not make these compulsory for course progression. The final part must be the end-of-course quiz. The end-of-course quiz is critical and standardised in terms of its content, and described in details below. This is because the completion of the quiz with a grade of over 50% correct answers will trigger the provision of completion badge and certificate to the learner.

Further information - other sources of information and further learning on Citizen Science. This can include links to other online courses and Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), training resources on the EU-Citizen.Science platform, and further reading, videos, and podcasts that are relevant to the topic.

Sources and acknowledgements - a list of sources that are used in the course, details of the people that created it, and funding sources that funded the work.

You can structure the rest of the sections to suit the content and can include activities that the learner should do (e.g. “write for yourself what your top priorities will be when managing data”); however, each section must end with a formative quiz (see details below).

Ensure that you have a clear structure/learning journey through the materials. The heading can be used to indicate the structure.

When designing activities, consider a range of activities - the types of activities can be:

- Assimilative - reading material, watching a video, or listening to a recording
- Finding and handling information - asking the learner to look out for information

- Productive - asking the learner to produce their own ideas or take notes
- Experiential - provide an opportunity for the learner to apply the knowledge in their own context
- Interactive/communicative - these are activities where learners can communicate with others, such as a discussion forum. However, this is more difficult to implement in an asynchronous situation so should be optional, if used at all.

Be aware that activities that allow learners to get feedback on how they are doing are popular, and in the context of the EU-Citizen.Science courses, a formative quiz will do this role.

Also be aware that the use of imagery - photographs, figures and illustrations - is favoured by learners. When designing the section, you can consider the use of decorative images that will represent the context of the specific section but be aware that they may disrupt learners' attention to the studies.

As you develop the details, regularly check your content against your learning outcomes. Ask someone else to look at your planning grid before you start writing the content.

As part of the planning, include assessment that will help the learner to check their progress. Well-designed online assessment activities such as polls, quizzes, questionnaires, reflective exercises and self-assessment questions can provide very effective consolidation and evidence of learning. In the EU-Citizen.Science training and educational modules we will use two forms of evaluation: formative and summative. Formative evaluation provides the learner with scope for self-reflection as they progress through the module - it can be a short quiz, for example, or a case study to consider and write about, followed by reading a "model answer" which reveals some points to think about. A formative quiz will not count towards the learner's grade but is aimed at providing the learner with a way to check that they understood the section. The formative quiz should have 2-4 questions, and the time that it takes to carry it out should be counted in the overall course plan. As noted, the end of the course is based on a well-constructed quiz covering material from the whole course is one method of conducting summative assessment in this situation.

Once the planning of the topic is complete, you can turn to the development of the content. It is highly recommended to continue and develop it in the design template, so you can refer back to the design guidelines, and have all the details in one place.

Accessibility - While all the training material should follow accessibility guidelines, we would especially emphasise:

- Each video or audio will require a script that can be shared for accessibility purposes.
- Ensure diagrams and schemas are explained in the text, and each image must use the alt-image tag to provide alternative description. Slides and material should be provided in accessible PDFs.

- The writing style for the material should pay attention to guidelines for writing for the web: use short sentences and style, use a conversational style that guide the reader to the course and remember that generally, each page should not contain more that 250 words to read (for a slow/non-native reader this is about two minutes, while for an average reader it will be about a minute). Do not use more than 500 words in one section. Avoid making sentences too long as this reduces their readability and accessibility, especially in an online setting when long sentences and paragraphs need to be broken into more manageable lengths.
- In quizzes, use drag and drop questions with care as they can be problematic on some devices and for participants who have dexterity limitations (e.g. tablets)

For more guidance on accessible material development, see the OpenLearn course ‘Accessibility of eLearning’²⁴.

While developing the detailed material, you will use different “assets” (e.g. resources from the EU-Citizen.Science platform, video on YouTube etc,) on a course, as long as their copyright status has been clarified and, ideally, unless they are available on a very stable platform such as YouTube, they should be copied and stored on the EU-Citizen.Science Moodle platform as to avoid deterioration of the course if the linked website disappears. Where necessary, indicate clearly that an external link is provided. In the template, you will find a space to plan and register the assets that will be used in a training unit. Before adopting an asset, ask yourself the following questions - Is it suitable for the audience? How complex is it? Is it answering your stated learning objective? How? Level of details and explanation? Anything missing that should be explained in text?

The table in the template for an asset register is taken from the Open University OpenLearnCreate course, and we provide here an explanation on what are the details that we recommend using.

Table 8: An example of an asset table.

Item	Explanation
Asset title	A description of the asset and its purpose
Long description	Used to describe diagrams, pictures, etc (useful for writing the visual description)
File type	e.g. PDF, jpg, doc ... This is to ensure that files are organised and stored on the system
File name	e.g. “CitizenScienceIntro.doc”

²⁴ <https://www.open.edu/openlearn/education-development/education-careers/accessibility-elearning/content-section-0>

Source URL	Where the asset was found/is hosted online
Location in course	Which subsection of the course, e.g. in Introduction, Topic 1, Summary
Rights/third party	Who owns the copyright - this can be useful for future update of the course
Clearance approved to release asset	E.g. Creative Commons license
URL in the course	For where the asset will appear in the course. It may be found on Google searches, even by a non-student.
Acknowledgements to be included in the course	What needs to be mentioned about this asset on the course acknowledgements page if the item belongs to a third party, or the organisation releasing it wishes to retain “All Rights Reserved” rather than using a Creative Commons license

Final Quiz - The final quiz is made of 10 questions. If the learner passes 50%, they can receive a certificate of completion of the course. The questions should be written bearing in mind Bloom’s taxonomy (see p39) and aim to be 30% on knowledge of issues covered in the course, 30% comprehension, 20% application and 20% analysis/synthesis. In the final quiz, the results are shown for the whole exam.

In the design of the question, we will follow the Open University checklist for quizzes:

- Identify the topics you want to cover in the quiz and write them down, you may do this as you are writing the course and the material is fresh in your mind.
- For each topic, draw up possible ways to ask the question, referring to examples of the different question types in use.
- Decide on the feedback type for each question.
- Draft questions for each topic in the question formats you have chosen.
- Write out some hint text for the interactive with multiple try questions.
- Write out some feedback text for the deferred feedback and immediate feedback questions.
- Compile all the questions and organise them into a logical order, grouping the random variant versions together under one question number (for example 3a, 3b, 3c each being a variant for question 3).
- Ask colleagues to review the questions and feedback text. Request that they provide comments on the pedagogical strength of the questions. Tell them about the potential audience for the open online course and the assessment strategy (including if the quiz is summative or formative).

- Review and, if necessary, revise the questions, feedback text and assessment strategy in light of comments from colleagues.

4.2.1. Content - uploading material to Moodle

Once the material for the course is ready, you can move to the development of the course.

In Moodle, you should see a container ready for your course (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Creating a Moodle course

The container is set for the number of sections that are included in the template documents and the four standard sections. Notice the Settings “cog” icon on the top right (see Figures 6 and 7).

Figure 7: Moodle course settings.

The first task to set for the course is under “More...”. In the course administration page, click on the “users” tab, and then on Enrolment methods. Notice the “eye” icon which indicates if the method is visible or not. For all EU-Citizen.Science modules, guest access should be visible, and self-enrolment must be visible. The order of enrolment should be Self, Guest, and Manual.

Figure 8: Moodle enrolment settings

Next, access the setting of “self-enrolment” and under “Enrolment Key” enter the enrolment key. No other changes are needed.

If your Moodle page does not seem to allow students to self-enrol, please use this article²⁵ for troubleshooting.

Now return to the course’s main page (using either the breadcrumbs or the sidebar on the left).

²⁵ <https://www.lmspulse.com/2018/moodle-for-beginners-how-to-enable-self-enrollment-in-your-moodle-course/>

On the main settings, click on “Turn Editing On”; this will enable you to start editing the course on Moodle. For a tutorial on how to use Moodle for additional content to a course, see the following resources:

- <https://www.youtube.com/c/moodle/videos>
- https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cEROJvmM5C8&list=PLxcO_MFWQBdfMnwMzFBq0ab9wSPniXEkp
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SbAPOjpNUrM>
- https://docs.moodle.org/39/en/Teacher_quick_guide

We now highlight specific aspects of editing that we recommend for the look and feel of EU-Citizen.Science training units.

For each topic:

- Use labels to indicate different activities within the topic, make the title a label that is medium heading. Indicate to people in each activity how long it should take (5 to 10 minutes in our cases). In labels and sub-headings, ensure that under “Activity Completion” the option “Do Not indicate activity completion”.
- Of the activities and resources that can be added to a course, we recommend only using the following activities: feedback, glossary, quiz and H5P activities, and file, label, page and URL in resources.
- We recommend using the H5P activities in order to make the content interactive.

As you design the course, consider how you can prevent learners from navigating away from the course when possible. For instance, if using third-party material, a video from YouTube, embedding these within the course is preferable to linking out and requiring students to leave the course/platform (whilst bearing in mind that this may have copyright implications). If you do require learners to leave the platform to access content, then it is advisable to suggest learners open the link in a new tab or window so that they can return to the course easily.

For quizzes, the tools that are suitable in Moodle are: Choice, Questionnaire can be used to gather information from learners and then show them other responses (so need seeding with some possible responses). Quizzes can be used for evaluation and to help learners to check their progression.

For formative learning quizzes linked to a specific section, we recommend - on the configuration page - setting the grade to “out of 10”, setting the layout to “never, all questions on one page”, setting question behaviour to “interactive with multiple tries”, as well as using encouraging and conversational language in the overall feedback messages. We suggest setting 50% as a grade counter.

The summative quiz should use “deferred feedback with CBM”, and in activity completion, set “show activity as complete when conditions are met” and tick “student must receive a grade to complete this

activity”.

In addition, under the “Review Options” make sure that all the following are ticked: “whether correct”, “specific feedback”, “general feedback”, “right answer” and “response history”.

We recommend that each module should include a feedback activity at the end, after the final quiz.

Once all the content is completed, we recommend beta-testing the module on someone who is not an expert on the subject, e.g. someone who does not work in that area.

In terms of accessibility, please note the core principles.

Do...		Don't...	
Use a combination of colour, shapes, and text to convey meaning			
Align all text left and use 1.5 line spacing			
Use headings in sentence case, sub-headings, and bullets to break up information			
Use heading styles in online text boxes and Microsoft Word documents	<code><h1></code> AaBbCc	Rely on text size and layout for structure	20pt, bold <u>Header</u>
Add alternative (alt) text to images and transcripts for videos	<code><alt></code>	Provide rich media content without a text alternative	
Use good colour contrasts and a readable font		Underline words, use italics, or write in capitals	<u>DON'T</u> <u>DO THIS</u>
Use a textbox to increase contrast between images and text			
Write descriptive and meaningful headings and hyperlinks	Contact us	Write uninformative links and headings	Click here
Add captions to audio and video content			

Figure 9: Core accessibility guidelines for the implementation. Source: UCL accessibility team

Proofreading and checking the material: proofread the text for consistency and sense; ensure that spelling and grammar are correct; ensure that the text adheres to any house style guides/conventions; check references and correct if necessary aim to identify open access ones; check cross-references and correct if necessary; check headings; check numbering and sequences; check web links.

Quality Assurance process: The course needs to be examined in several devices. The main points - check for navigation through the course; accessibility (alt-text, transcripts); copyright; keeping learners within the course (instructions for external links in new window); check audio and video; provide alternative formats; check that budges work.

Have a simple survey of demographic information of participants without asking for a name - you and other course administrators will need to agree to a standard questionnaire for modules.

4.3. Best practice for creating online learning content: feedback from the Consortium

On 18th and 19th June 2020 an online workshop was held with project partners to gather information on online learning experiences, and ideas for future modules. Please see section 2.2.2 for further details.

Feedback from Task A: Online learning as an experience

24 people across the Consortium (excluding Muki Haklay and Alice Sheppard, who designed and ran the activities) took part in contributing to a Google document, each anonymously. This was achieved by providing a numbered table. Each participant was asked to choose a number and, next to that number, assign themselves an obvious pseudonym (for example, “Spaghetti Monster”), and to use that name and/or number in the Google document at appropriate places. The purpose of the humorous anonymity was to encourage unpressured thinking and honest reporting of negative experiences. The Google document’s activities were laid out in tables, so it was easy for each individual to find the place for themselves to write in.

Task A consisted of a numbered table (so, for example, “Loch Ness Monster”, who was no. 6, would go to the sixth row in the table) with three columns. At the top of each column was a question. The questions were as follows:

- Q1. Have you ever done a self-directed course, i.e. without a tutor and with automatic marking? What was the subject?
- Q2. What is a good thing that you can share about self-directed learning? What is the best practice?
- Q3. What is a bad thing that you can share about self-directed learning? What could have been done better?

The first two rows were filled out in advance as examples and written in a playful style. The purpose of this activity was to gather people's honest feelings about online courses that do not have a tutor or even a virtual classroom setting: i.e. that are done in the individual's own time, alone and without any interaction besides some automated feedback. This will be the style in which EU-Citizen.Science's training modules will have to run, because there is no budget for tuition, and this will especially be the case after the completion of this project when the platform is self-sustaining. It is important to understand the pitfalls of self-directed learning and find out what makes a self-directed course enjoyable, memorable, useful and easy to complete.

Several Consortium members had never done such an online course. Modules people reported having done included work-related (e.g. fire safety, GDPR, evaluation, ethics, "British Values"); languages; ICT and coding; work skills such as typing or social media; and topics of personal interest such as birdsong identification, music and anthropology.

Reports of useful or enjoyable aspects (from Q2) included:

- The ability to do the course in your own time (this was the most mentioned)
- An attractive presentation: for example, colours and layout, a humorous element to features such as reminders, or the enthusiastic manner of video presenters
- The presence of a discussion forum in which you could interact with other learners doing a similar course
- Activities being short and tasks small and manageable
- Some praised courses which had a competitive element - including competition with your own past scores. Conversely, others praised a lack of competition, which took the pressure off and did not reward "cutting corners"
- A scoring system which identified the learner's weaknesses and was able to direct them to focus on these
- Being permitted to skip irrelevant sections
- Having optional extra materials to read outside the course
- Prompt grades/rewards for work
- Frequent questions in order to encourage understanding
- Diversity of activities and materials, such as video/audio/text
- A sense of progress, such as "unlocking levels", or demonstrating competence at one activity in order to gain access to a more difficult one
- The ability to go back and revisit material where necessary
- The ability to share the course and invite others to join it

Features and elements of such learning which were reported as less enjoyable (from Q3) included:

- Boredom (especially in courses required by one's workplace)
- A lack of clarity about assessment, or a feeling that there was no real assessment
- Rushing through difficult concepts without giving the learner time to practice

- A lack of structure and guidance
- The ability to do the course in one's own time. Although this was mostly seen as a positive, it also ran the risk of encouraging procrastination, loneliness and a lack of motivation
- A lack of genuine connection with the subject - a feeling of "just click through it"
- Being forced to interact with other participants (called "social learning" in the OpenLearn course mentioned in Section 4.1.2). Although a discussion forum was mostly seen as a positive, a few people saw it as a negative when they felt they had little in common with other learners
- Unnecessary complexity or difficulty of tasks, especially where the main difficulty was the technical skill required rather than the subject matter!
- Having nowhere to go for help when a concept was difficult to understand
- Content being out of date or "too easy"; not learning anything new
- Materials all being too similar, e.g. all video
- A lack of follow-up, e.g. future courses or obvious ways to implement new learning
- A lack of discussion with peers and tutor; lacking a sense of community
- A lack of feedback
- A lack of human incentive; the need to be entirely self-motivated

Some of the points are opposites - for example, the issue of doing the course in one's own time, or the presence or absence of a discussion forum, were seen as advantages by some people and as disadvantages by others. The OpenLearn course stated that enforced social learning is very unpopular and can prevent people from finishing a course, as not everybody feels comfortable posting on a discussion forum, and it is difficult to set a clear task involving such a forum. Nevertheless, enough people remarked on the benefits of having some interaction available that it is clear that it is a valuable option.

Feedback was mentioned frequently, and many platforms have several methods of offering feedback - whether these are simple, such as the instant marking of a multiple choice or true/false quiz, or more complex, for example "the use of AI with funny reminders worked super good for me in Gymlish".

Particularly frequently mentioned was that tasks should be frequent and short and simple to do, particularly where feedback was prompt and where weaknesses could be identified and tackled. Much of this can be automated with most platforms, and quizzes can carry a variety of styles, from simple questions to drag-and-drop text boxes to crosswords.

Material being "too easy" was mentioned far more frequently than material being "too difficult". In fact, only one person mentioned difficulty and that was clearly more in the context of the task and the ICT skills required to complete the task, rather than the subject matter. We can therefore assume that most learners who come to our courses will know some of the basics, and we should not be afraid to present some relatively in-depth or complex material.

Task B invited participants to suggest future training modules, along with specific activities, the intended audience, and how their module would fill a gap in CS training and educational material. The results of this part of the workshop are discussed in section 2.1.4 and shown in Table 1.

5. Summary and next steps

5.1. Training & Educational Material Needs

- Training resources were historically indexed under Resources on the Platform. In the forthcoming release of the Platform they will now have their own section and will be referred to as Training & Educational Material.
- Training & Educational Material is defined as: “*Material that is designed or can be used explicitly for the goals of teaching or training a person on the practice of citizen science e.g. how to design and implement a volunteer-based activity, how to control data quality, the ethical and legal requirements of working with volunteers and managing their data. These can include massive open online courses (MOOCs), workshops, webinars, gamified training, and quizzes.*” It is important to note that at the present time the Training & Educational Material section of the website will be solely reserved for material that is about the design and implementation of citizen science as a practice and not for very specific activities such as how to carry out a soil survey or how to identify marine fish.
- The main descriptors used when referring to training and educational material are:
 - Theme: specifies a topic within CS (e.g. engagement, data quality and standards, regulations, and ethics).
 - Audience: specifies the type of audience that the material should cater for e.g. policymakers, citizen science practitioners.
 - Domain of Scientific Activity: specifies the field or discipline that the material relates to e.g. Astronomy, Education.
 - Format & Type: specifies the format (e.g. lecture, MOOC) and type (e.g. Text) of material.
- Question phrasing meant we were unable to carry out a complete needs analysis of community needs of material format and type. In the meantime, the vocabulary for the material type will follow the DCMI type vocabulary, however, for Platform usability it would be useful to understand if this vocabulary is well understood by the community.
- Based on the gap and needs analyses, we have identified the following modules that will be developed:

- Introduction to citizen science for journalists - this unit is aimed at journalists and it will include material to inform journalists about the field of citizen science, and how they can utilise it in their reporting and in developing new news stories.
 - Training the trainers in citizen science - this unit is aimed at practitioners and explains the methodology of using the “train the trainers” in environmental citizen science projects.
 - Introduction to citizen science for everyone - this unit is aimed at the public and will provide an hour long course that will introduce them to the concept of citizen science and how they can find projects that will interest them and be relevant to them.
 - Using citizen science in school - an introduction to the use of citizen science within the school context (from early years education to high school) and examples of activities that are relevant in this context. The course is aimed at teachers.
 - Working with volunteers in citizen science - communication and feedback. Training for all audiences on how to keep volunteers engaged.
 - Why trust citizen science data? A course aimed at policy makers and civil servants in the field of environmental management and explains aspects of data quality in citizen science.
 - Communication skills for citizen science practitioners - provision of introduction to science communication for people who are initiating and running Citizen Science projects, including communicating with participants, with news organisations, and with public authorities. Special attention on communicating results.
 - Achieving policy impact with Citizen Science - a unit aimed at policy makers, civil servants, and practitioners. The focus is on the role of Citizen Science within policy processes and how to reach decision makers and design projects in a way that can have policy impact.
 - Doing Citizen Science ethically - an introduction to the ethical principles of running Citizen Science projects and introduction to tools and techniques that should be used such as informed consent.
 - Creating high quality data in environmental Citizen Science projects - Training for scientists and practitioners on how to create projects with high quality data, and tools, methods, stats and data techniques for quality assurance.
- Additional gaps that were identified in the workshop and are not included in the list of courses, but will be considered later include:
 - Appropriate metrics for evaluating and measuring CS impacts (particularly societal) and how to measure.
 - Training for scientists on an introduction to CS and themes of interest.
 - A basic introduction on the methods for scientific investigation.

- Training on research design and suitable methods in an accessible format.
 - Training for citizens on how to design a CS project.
 - CS in museums.
 - Transferability of CS to other potential domains (e.g. language learning and teaching) and scientific disciplines.
- The number of requests for material targeting different audience types may not reflect the way in which the development of material should be prioritised. Future analyses of this type should aim to capture the priority of requests and should be carried out on a regular basis to capture the evolving nature of the CS landscape.

5.2. Metadata

- For usability, the mandatory metadata fields will include the four main descriptors used by the survey community: Theme, Audience, Domain of Scientific Activity and Format/ Type.
- Where practical we have tried to identify vocabularies for each of the metadata fields that aligns with the terminology in common usage by the respondents we surveyed but established metadata standards in an effort to maximise interoperability.
- Mandatory metadata fields are:
 - Title: the name of the item. This is a free text field.
 - Description: short description that summarises the item. This is a free text field.
 - Keywords: keywords or tags used to describe the content. This is a free text field.
 - Resource Format: the format of the training material (e.g. moving image, text). This field follows the DCMI Type Vocabulary.
 - Learning Resource Type: the type of learning material (e.g. MOOC, handout). This is a free text field.
 - Theme: describes the theme of the material (e.g. research design and methods, engagement). This follows the vocabulary developed in D3.2 and is based on thematic analysis of the existing resources on the Platform.
 - Topic: this describes the scientific topic addressed by the material. This field follows the PPSR Topic vocabulary
 - URL: the URL at which the training material can be found. This is a free text field.

- Language: describes the main language of the material. This field provides language codes from the IETF BCP 47 standard.
- Publisher: the publisher of the material. This is a free text field.
- Audience: describes the intended audience of the material. This field uses the vocabulary developed in D3.2 from a thematic analysis respondents descriptions of target audiences.
- Image: This is an image to represent the training material.

5.3. Module content and technical design

- Module content:
 - Each module should take 1-2 hours to complete - but probably 10-20 hours to design.
 - Modules are self-learned, without instructors, and assessment will be by a quiz. The modules must therefore contain well-thought-out tasks and links to resources to assist the learner in finding any information they need.
 - Content will need to be interesting and engaging, to be attractive to students.
 - Each module should contain 5-8 sections, which must include the standard “Welcome and introduction”, “Conclusion and self-assessment”, “Further information and learning” and “Sources and acknowledgements”.
 - Each module must contain two or three learning objectives and learning outcomes. Learning objectives show the purpose of the course, while learning outcomes indicate what the student will have learned, or be able to do, after the course. All sections of the course will need to relate to the learning objectives. It is recommended that guidance on designing learning objectives and outcomes is followed (see section 4.1.2).
 - Assessment can be formative (which allows the learner to check how they are doing) or summative (that grades them after part or all of the course).
 - The end-of-course quiz should contain 10 questions; if a learner gets 50%, they will be able to get a badge to indicate that they have passed the course.
 - Content should be taken from a wide range of sources - it will be worth it to do a “literature search” of your own when planning course content.
 - It will be worthwhile to ask someone else to read or beta-test your course before publishing it, and to examine the content.
 - It will be necessary to plan the content extensively, continually checking it against learning objectives and for variety.
- Module design
 - The course description should be written with SEO in mind, as well as telling the potential learner what they will get out of the course.

- Accessibility is vital - images should have text descriptions available, slides should be made available as downloadable PDFs, etc.
- Sound quality is very important, while research shows that learners have more relaxed expectations of video quality (due to the popularity of making videos for social media); therefore, it will be perfectly acceptable to make a video yourself using basic equipment to introduce the course.
- Visual imagery is very popular with learners, including pictures simply to illustrate a point being made, even if it is not vital.
- A variety of materials should be used, such as video, images, text, diagrams, graphs, etc.
- Videos should not be more than 5 minutes long; 2 ½ minutes is shown by research to be the ideal length.
- Tasks should be frequent, short and simple, as a way for the learner to check their understanding.
- Feedback should be as frequent as possible, even just from yes/no answers.
- A variety of tasks should be used - quizzes, asking the learner to take notes or write something (this would not be marked, but they could be given a “model” answer after their attempt), crossword/drag and drop, etc.
- A task could also be communicative; the EU-Citizen.Science platform will contain a discussion forum where learners can interact with each other to share tips, but this will not work well if made compulsory, given that all learners will be taking the courses alone and in their own time.
- Courses should be split into sections, and learners enjoy the sense of progression from one section to the next, rather like “unlocking a level”.
- It will be vital to plan the exact timings of every section of the course, including reading and quiz-taking, so that the total time spent will be 1-2 hours.
- We strongly recommend that you take the OpenLearn course “How to make an open online course”.

6. Appendices

6.1. Appendix 1 - Glossary of themes that describe training materials (taken from Table 4 in D3.2).

Resource needs theme	Description
Best practices	Resources that provide well-tested methodologies or tools that have been successfully implemented and that are also well-documented; also includes reviews and articles about well tested methodologies or tools that have been successfully implemented and can serve as examples for others.

Co-creation	Resources that provide and/or analyse methods for collaborative design, creation and development in CS; can range from platforms like Github to templates to specific group facilitation methods for co-creation.
Communication	Resource that provide tools and approaches for communication in CS; can address communication strategies to reach different stakeholder and target audiences, tools (for how) to set up a communication campaign; descriptions and guidelines for different forms of communication (e.g., storytelling, visualisations, videos, text, images, diagrams, etc); analysis of communication in CS and links to science communication.
CS stories	Resources that offer insights that may not regularly be covered in CS case studies, or other forms of project overviews, e.g. personal stories about people's motivations, feelings or experiences in CS (e.g., an Instagram account of a CS project, that regularly provides photos and snap-shot experiences of volunteers).
Data quality and standards	Resources that offer insights, methods and tools on how to address data quality (e.g. how to reach and describe desired data quality levels) and data standards (how to work with and implement existing data standards, how to create new standards) in CS.
Empowerment	Resources that provide methods or tools to specifically enable certain audiences and groups to take part in CS, that would otherwise be excluded and where CS provides a means for these groups to be heard and their needs and problems to be recognised; resources that address the value added and added impact of CS and CS data to an existing cause or activity; also, resources that specifically address how to kick-start of CS projects from scratch in challenging contexts or environments (e.g. when faced with regulatory or social restrictions).
Engagement	Resources that provide approaches or tools (for how) to engage diverse audiences in CS; also includes reports or evaluations on audience and stakeholder engagement in CS.
Evaluation of CS	Resources that provide insight, tools and/or methods to evaluate CS projects; i.e. that help define and monitor targets, indicators and different success metrics.
Event planning	Resources that provide insights, tools and/or guidelines for event planning and implementation as well as event communication in CS.
Impact	Resources that provide insight, tools and/or methods to understand, document and communicate impact in CS; can include tools, instructions and reflections on how to define and trace impact, how to define impact indicators, and how to measure and document them, how to communicate them, how to make impact assessment comprehensible and transparent.
Instructables	Any resources that come in form of an instruction that can be followed in a step-by-step fashion (e.g., protocols, tutorials, apps with forms to fill); resources that aim at providing clear descriptions for how to implement something.
Introduction to CS	Resources that provide an introduction to CS, characterised by providing a general overview; can be to theory of CS, or practice and application; tools that help understand the basics of CS, or that help get started with CS.

Link with formal education	Resources that address the link between CS and formal education, e.g. tools and resources for integrating CS into school curricula, lesson plans for CS projects in schools, CS toolkits for schools and instructions on how to do CS in class, best practices and experiences on doing CS in schools, reports and evaluations of CS and CS learning in schools etc.; can also include tools for doing CS that work well in the classroom.
Project management	Resources that provide specific insights, methods and/or tools for project management of CS projects, focusing on the practice of coordinating and leading the work of a team to achieve goals and meet success criteria at a specified time; can include aspects such as budget and staff planning and monitoring, team coordination and team communication, collaborative work and conflict resolution, time planning and progress monitoring of tasks, planning, launching and implementation of different project stages etc.
Project sustainability	Resources that provide insight, tools and/or approaches to make projects last long(er), or how to ensure uptake and exploitation of results, or how to facilitate transition to new projects.
Reflections on science	Resources that offer reflections or methods for reflecting on science and the scientific method more generally; can include how to question and remain critical of scientific findings, introduction to science, evidence-based approaches, biases in science, uncertainties in science etc.
Regulations and ethics	Resources that offer insights, methods and tools to understand, address and integrate regulations and ethics in CS (e.g., GDPR compliance, ethical research, open science etc).
Research design and methods	Resources that address the specificities of research design and research methods in CS; includes description and/or analysis of approaches for research design and research methods development in CS, potentially covering all stages of the research process; also includes tools and resources used as part of conducting the research; depending on the research objective, specific tools can include tools for data collection, sampling, chats, forums, etc.
Transferability	Resources that provide insight, reflections, tools and/or approaches to applying CS methodologies/tools developed and tested in one domain or scientific field to be used in another; or to implementing CS in new fields entirely, where the application of CS is new and unprecedented.

6.2. Appendix 2: Example design template: introduction to citizen science for journalists

Version 1 - August 2020

6.2.1. Core information

Course name: Introduction to citizen science for journalists

Intended audience: journalists - especially in the fields of science, technology, environment, and health that want to learn the basics of citizen science for the purpose of dealing with an assignment.

Course description: This is a free course of an hour and a half, that provides an introduction to citizen science, which is a form of active public engagement in science.

It is designed to assist journalists, who need to understand citizen science in their reporting, and no prior knowledge in science reporting is needed for this course.

The interest in citizen science, the number of projects, and the number of people who participate in such activities have grown significantly over the last decade. This course will introduce you to core aspects of the field, the activities that fall under it, issues that are frequently discussed about citizen science (data quality and motivation), and the type of stories that are commonly told about citizen science activities.

The enrollment key to this course is: CitSciNews

[150 words - first sentence always the same “This is a free course of an hour/2 hours”, second describes who the course is for and if any prior knowledge. Third explaining the significance of the course and why the learner should take it, and then the topics that are covered in the course. Finally the enrollment key]

Course image:

[Image properties aspect ratio: Size:]

Source: UCL ExCiteS. **Alt-Text:** white camper van with different science and do-it-yourself symbols parked in front of a high rise building. This is the science bus of the Doing-It-Together Science project.

Course length: 1.5h (additional material for 2h) [Indicate the length of time that the module requires]

Learning outcomes:

By the end of this course, the learner will:

Objective 1: be able to explain the historical background and current activities in citizen science, by identifying key terms and concepts

Objective 2: Identify the major challenges in citizen science projects, including data quality, motivation, working with volunteers, and sharing information

Objective 3: analyse the contexts in which citizen science can be integrated within news stories

[Set 2-3 objectives, see guidance document on developing learning outcomes]

6.2.2. Main division - topics

How many topics (sections) are in the course? 5 [+4 standard sections]

Provide a title and a short description for each section:

[Notice that “Welcome and introduction”, “Conclusion and self-assessment”, “Further information and learning”, “Sources and acknowledgement” are mandatory and part of every module]

Welcome and introduction to the course - introduction to the course from the course tutor. Overview of the content and the learning outcomes. Teaser and a sample story of citizen science achievements

Section 1: *citizen science in five stories*: a description of historical examples of activities that will be called citizen science, and an overview of the type of activities that people engage in citizen science.

Section 2: *terminology*: to assist the process of learning about citizen science, we introduce common terms that are being used to describe citizen science, and some of the issues with these terms (e.g. the term “citizen” in the US)

Section 3: *challenges and opportunities in citizen science*: issues that are commonly discussed with citizen science - data quality, engagement with volunteers, motivations, opportunities that citizen science offer in terms of engagement, science literacy, awareness to issues, skills

Section 4: *Social and political impacts*: an overview of the impacts that participation in citizen science can lead - awareness and science literacy to impacts on policy and information that contribute to climate change studies.

Section 5: *citizen science in the news*: introduction to some of the existing use of citizen science in journalism and the type of stories that can be told about citizen science activities. Organisations and individuals that can be contacted for commentary on citizen science

Section 6: n/a

Section 7: n/a

Section 8: n/a

Summary and self-assessment - summary of the course and end-of-course quiz

Further information - other sources of information and further learning on citizen science

Sources and acknowledgement - a list of sources that are used in the course.

Each section should have a title and a short explanation of about a sentence or two.

6.2.3. Detailed course plan

[Example]

SECTION ONE: Title of topic (XX Minutes)

What can we expect to learn from this section?

What?	How?	Why?
1.1 The content or task you're proposing to include, e.g. Introduction to the course: structure, practical, assignment, reading and use of Moodle.(x minutes)	The means by which you aim to deliver it, e.g. a talking head style video of module leader explaining the course focus and approach. Be as specific as you can.	Rationale for inclusion, e.g. to situate learners and set expectations for engagement.

Welcome and introduction to the course (6 minutes)

What can we expect to learn from this section?

Introduction to the course from the course tutor. Overview of the content and the learning outcomes.
Teaser and a sample story of citizen science achievements

What?	How?	Why?
I.1 Introduction from the course tutor (2 minutes)	A one-minute video, introducing the course to the learner. Introduction of who made the course, and what is covered in it.	Welcome the student, and provide assurance about the credibility of the course
I.2 Course overview (2 minutes)	Overview of the course structure in text and a slides+audio - explaining the	Familiarity with the mezzo-structure of

	elements that will appear in each class	the course and the reason to learn in
I.3 An example of citizen science achievements (2 minutes)	Provide an example of what is included in citizen science using the NSF video https://youtu.be/5ijSk-QWwjw	Make the course interesting and worth exploring

Section 1: Citizen science in five stories (18 minutes) *What can we expect to learn from this section?*

a description of historical examples of activities that will be called citizen science, and an overview of the type of activities that people engage in citizen science.

What?	How?	Why?
1.1 Introduction to the section (2min)	Text, explaining how we are going to cover the history of citizen science in ten stories	Explaining to the learner why it is worth following it
1.2 One (2 min) - Mary Anning and Lyme Regis dinosaurs	Telling the story of Mary Anning and her discoveries. Text and image 250 words	Demonstration of exclusion from scientific practice and the ability of people from all walks of life to contribute
1.3 Two (2 min) - Fred and Moonwatch	Telling the story of how volunteers spotted the first satellite. Text and image 250 words	Demonstration of the contribution of citizen science at the time of big science and the beginning of space exploration
1.4 Three (2 min) - Big Garden Birdwatch	Telling the story of a national scale citizen science project that educate young people and engage families. Text and image 250 words	Large scale, education focus project

1.5 Four (2 min) - Kevin, Chris and the galaxies	Telling the story of zooniverse as an example of crowdsourcing. Text and image 250 words	The power of the internet and crowdsourcing
1.6 Five (2 min) - Shannon and DIY science	Telling the story of Public Lab as an example for bottom up, environmental justice focused project	Community driven and environmentally focused case
1.7 Overview of citizen science activities today (4 minutes)	Bringing the stories together and introducing some key terms - volunteer thinking or collective intelligence, ecological observation, community science	Helping the learner to link up the different examples and bring them together
1.8 Summary (1 min)	Explaining the learning from the session	
1.9 Quiz (3 min)	3 examples of activities that are similar to those in the session	Test the understanding of the type of activities in citizen science

Summary and Self-Assessment (10 minutes)

What can we expect to learn from this section?

Summary of the course and end-of-course quiz

What?	How?	Why?
S.1 Summary of the issues that were covered, guidance to material in further information and in the acknowledgment and sources (5 minutes)	Summary of the issues that were covered in each section, with the main “take away” points	Helping the learner to identify the most critical content
I.2 Course quiz (5 minutes)	Final review of the course, and credit for successful completion	Testing the knowledge in the module

Further information (5 minutes+)

What can we expect to learn from this section?

Other sources of information and further learning on citizen science

What?	How?	Why?
F.1 More sources of information that can expand the knowledge on the module through other training opportunities such as MOOCs (5 minutes)	Links and details of other online courses and places where more learning can be gained	Allow the learner to take the next step
I.2 Other sources of information (5 minutes)	Details of books, articles and other information that can be used to develop an understanding of the topic	Providing the learner with further information that is not linked to learning

Final Quiz structure

The final is made of 10 questions. If the learner pass 50%, they can get a certificate of completion of the course. The questions should use Bloom's taxonomy, and aim to be 30% on knowledge of issues covered in the course, 30% comprehension, 20% application and 20% analysis/synthesis. The questions should follow the taxonomy.

What?	How? Type of question	Why?
1 The five cases that were introduced in part one are related to five common terms that describe similar practices today, can you associate them?		Testing comprehension of topic 1
2		
3		
4		
5		
6		
7		
8		
9		
10		

6.2.4. Equality Impact Assessment

Characteristics	Issues and mitigation
Age	Ensure that material is inclusive for different age groups. This course is aimed at acting journalists, who will be within working ages (25-70) and therefore the material should be presented in a way that is suitable for this group. The font should be readable to older adults.
Disability	There is a need to ensure that a learner with disability can access the material. Care will be given for visually impaired learners, and also to those that are having dexterity issue in the selection of questions and options in quizzes and in interactive parts
Race	Citizen science has underrepresentation of people from Black backgrounds, and the material should include recognition of disparities and the potential for inclusiveness
Religion and Belief	The text should be written in a way that it recognises differences in religious beliefs
Sex (Gender)	Gender issues in science are well established and the examples that will be used in the unit should balance gender and provide appropriate role models
Sexual orientation	The material should not be prejudiced against people with different sexual orientation

6.2.5. Digital Assets Register

For each asset that you are planning to use, fill in the metadata in the following structure:

Name and description	Course cover image - Science Bus
File type	jpg
File name	

Source URL	None
Location in the course	Cover image of the course
Rights	CC-By
Attribution for third part asset	UCL ExCiteS
Clearance/approval for use	Approved
URL in the course	
Acknowledgement	(cc-by 4.0 UCL ExCiteS)

Name and description	NSF citizen science video
File type	YouTube link
File name	
Source URL	https://youtu.be/5ijSk-QWwjw
Location in the course	Introduction to the course
Rights	Copyright, can be freely distributed in its entirety
Attribution for third part asset	US National Science Foundation
Clearance/approval for use	Provided in the video
URL in the course	
Acknowledgement	

Notes for digital assets (source: OpenLearn, Open University, UK):

- name/title of asset (describe the asset)
- long description (for images and diagrams)
- file type (e.g. PDF, jpg, doc, ppt, xls, audio or video file)
- filename (e.g. DCN1234.jpg)
- source URL (where you found the asset online)
- location(s) in course (in which section / subsection)

- rights/third party (who owns the copyright - even if all the assets are owned by you or your organisation it is a good idea to record this in the asset register)
- attribution to use with third party asset
- clearance approved to release asset as Creative Commons (you can use this for notes about the clearance and date of clearance)
- URL in the course (URL for where the asset will appear in the course)
- acknowledgements to be included in the course (what needs to be listed about this asset on the acknowledgements page if the item belongs to a third party or if the organisation releasing the course wishes to retain 'All rights reserved' rather than use a Creative Commons licence for this asset)

6.2.6. Detail course content

Section 1: Citizen science in five stories

I.1 Introduction from the course tutor (2 minutes)

Transcript:

I.2 Course overview (2 minutes)

Text + Image

I.3 An example of citizen science achievements (2 minutes)

6.3. Course design checklist (based on UCL's Connected Learning Baseline document)

Adapted from a checklist by Matt S. Smith and Anna Trostnikova, Faculty of Engineering Sciences, UCL

6.3.1. Navigation

This is how students find and interact with information and resources on your course.

<p>A1. Set your course format as 'Collapsed Topics' – This format is more accessible on mobile devices and for those using screen readers. This can be done in the Settings for your course.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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<p>A2. Add meaningful section headings to each topic/section – follow format ‘Topic 1: [Title]’, ‘Topic 2: [Title]’, etc.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>A3. Write ‘section’ introductory text – include a short introductory paragraph giving an overview of the topic’s learning.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>A4. Use sub-headings within sections/topics – ensure you keep to a consistent heading hierarchy. Main titles – H3, sub-titles – H4, H5, H6.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>A5. Use default text colours – do not change text colours.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>A6. Organise tasks in a meaningful and clearly structured way – This may be chronologically (the order in which to complete tasks), which is highly recommended for wholly online module delivery. Headings should be used to group learning resources and activities.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>A7. Minimise cognitive overload and use Pages to reduce the length of sections – if you have over 250 words of text, put it on a Moodle Page so that there’s a link to it (rather than having all the text displayed on the main page. Too much text on the home page, is sometimes called the ‘scroll of death’!. Also, name the Moodle Page to indicate its content.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>A9. Clearly NUMBER all resources and activities – e.g. ‘<i>Task 1.1 - Your first citizen science experience</i>’.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>A10. Meaningfully LABEL all resources and activities with descriptive titles – e.g. ‘<i>Task 1.1. - Your first citizen science experience</i>’. Titles should at a glance make sense to learners providing them with the information needed to know what the resource or activity is without opening it. Titles such as ‘Task 1’ are not adequate. The description should provide further details about the resource/activity and how it related to the intended learning outcomes.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>

<p>A11. Add word counts and time lengths to resources – e.g. ‘<i>Task 2.3 - Nature article: Semiconductors (2000 words)</i>’ or ‘<i>Task 3.3 - The Real Iron Man (6m)</i>’. Timings should be included for videos and word counts for readings. This allows learners to decide whether they have time to undertake a piece of learning before opening it. Each resource / activity should also have an accompanying description.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>A12. Clearly label optional activities/resources – e.g ‘<i>Task 3.2 - The life of Mary Anning (optional)</i>’. If you have multiple optional resources/tasks, perhaps put them into their own section which is provided at the end of the course</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>A13. Check and fix or remove broken hyperlinks (URLs)</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>A14. Check that all resources are up-to-date before releasing them to learners.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>

6.3.2. Introduction

These are the things that will help learners orientate themselves at the beginning of the course.

<p>B1. Make a short ‘Welcome’ video – available to <i>learners</i> at the beginning of the module. This helps to create a connection with the <i>learners</i> .</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>B2. Include measurable module level learning outcomes (CLB 2.1) – In order to ensure they are measurable, use of a Bloom’s Taxonomy verb table is recommended.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<p>B3. Include Course Summary – ensure you have included a short course summary (which learners see when searching for the module via Moodle Search).</p>	<input type="checkbox"/>

6.3.3. Communication

These are ways to promote effective communication between tutors and students, and students with their peers.

C1. Module evaluation – include an online module evaluation form so students can evaluate the module. Use Moodle Questionnaire to do this.	<input type="checkbox"/>
C2. Adopt a welcoming and approachable tone	<input type="checkbox"/>
C3. Provide opportunities for learners to feedback	<input type="checkbox"/>

6.3.4. Accessibility

This is how to make your course accessible to different learners. This may include those accessing your course using different devices e.g. mobile, as well as those with additional educational needs e.g. dyslexia.

D1. Provide a course level accessibility statement – Provide a brief, course-level accessibility statement containing any additional guidance and indicating the availability of an alternative format for any resource.	<input type="checkbox"/>
D2. Accessibility Fundamentals – Covers: fonts (size and style), text (colours and contrast), spacing, links, images, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
D2.1. Ensure fonts are large enough and sans serif – they should be at least pt11.	<input type="checkbox"/>
D2.2. Ensure coloured text has high contrast – against backgrounds. Avoid red, green and pink text.	<input type="checkbox"/>
D2.3. Ensure links are descriptive – (avoiding “click here”) and open in the same window.	<input type="checkbox"/>
D2.4. Use alt text descriptions for images – mention the key learning points, for screen-reader users (e.g., alongside the image, as a caption, or as ‘alternative text’).	<input type="checkbox"/>

D4. Audio and video accessibility pointers - Provide transcripts and alternative formats	<input type="checkbox"/>
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6.3.5. Legal issues

Good copyright practices, data protection issues and ensuring students have a private (password protected) environment to work in.

H1. Observe intellectual property and copyright legislation	<input type="checkbox"/>
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